

The Effects of Workforce Diversity on Employee Performance: A Study on the Selected Pharmaceutical Firms of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Diversity means understanding that each individual is unique, and recognizing our individual differences. These can be along the dimensions of race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, age, physical abilities, religious beliefs, political beliefs, or other ideologies. The main objective of this study was to determine the effect of work diversity on employee performance in the pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh. The study also sought to determine the effect of education diversity, ethnic diversity, gender diversity and age diversity on employee performance in the Pharmaceutical industry in Bangladesh. A descriptive research design was used in this research. The study target population was all the managers working at the headquarters of all the pharmaceutical farms of Bangladesh. This study used non probability random sampling and snowballing sample method to fill up the questionnaire. The sample size of this study was therefore 50 workers of most renowned pharmaceutical farms of Bangladesh

Keywords: Race, Ethnicity, Economic Status, Pharmaceutical Industry

1. Introduction

Workforce diversity refers to organizations that are becoming more heterogeneous with the mix of people in terms of gender, age, race, and education background (Robbins, 2009). Technological advancement and the introduction of a global economy bring the people of the world closer together than ever before. Organizations that can develop and use the necessary policies and procedures to do this will preserve a competitive advantage among their counterparts and increase their effectiveness. To achieve success and maintain a competitive advantage, we must be able to draw on the most important resource such as the skills of the workforce. With the increasing richness of diversity in the workforce, we need to expand our outlook and use creative strategies to be successful. A diverse workforce for instance, includes gender, age, ethnicity, and education background. According to Robbins (2009) workforce diversity has important implications toward management practices and policies. Workforce diversity is a global workplace and marketplace topic. Any business that intends to be successful must have a borderless view and an underlying commitment to ensuring that workforce diversity is part of its day-today business conduct (Childs, 2005).

Erasmus (2007) mentioned that diversity management and workforce diversity is a forced integration that creates conflict and uncertainty in the workforce as leadership is not skilled in the discipline of diversity management and its principles. Hilary and Elaine (2000) suggested that organizations should embrace diversity in their workforce and work towards achieving it by creating a culture where difference can thrive, rather than working simply for representatives and assimilation. According to Dahm (2003), diversity within the workplace can evoke an array of emotions as, some view diversity as something to be dealt rather than a tool to be used to improve the organization. As a conclusion, decades of research on the effects of diversity within teams and small groups indicate that diversity can have negative effects, as well as positives ones (Kochan et al., 2003). Moreover they elaborated that the lack of evidence linking workforce diversity to employee performance may be that the relationship between diversity and the bottom line is more complex than is implied by the popular discussion. Therefore, this study focuses on the relationship among gender, age, ethnicity, and education background towards employee's performance in an organization.

2. Problem Statement

Diversity within the work place can evoke an array of emotions as some view diversity as something to be dealt rather than a tool to be used to improve the organization. Even though, many will agree that the results of a

diversity-conscious organization add value to the employee and organization, yet research evaluating diversity for the sake of developing methods of interventions does not exist.

This study explored the impact of gender, age, and education background on employee performance in the Bangladeshi Pharmaceutical industry which is renowned to employ highly diversified workforce. The challenge and problems faced as a result of incorporating work place diversity under one roof can be turned into a strategic organizational asset if organizations are able to capitalize on this melting pot of diverse talents. With the mixture of talents of diverse cultural backgrounds, genders, ages, and lifestyles, an organization can respond to business opportunities more rapidly and creatively, especially in the global area which must be one of the important organizational goals to be attained. Bangladeshi Pharmaceutical companies are expanding their business and exporting products in other countries rapidly, Many people from different educational background and different ages of people are working in Pharmaceuticals firms of our country, On the other hand Participation of female workers are increasing day by day .

3. Objectives of the Study

Workplace diversity is a multi-faceted concept that will continue to evolve as more industries, specifically the pharmaceutical industry. Workforce diversity becomes inevitable and fundamental for sustainable organizational performance. The objectives of this study were given below:

3.1 General Objective

The general objective of the study was to identify the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance of selected Pharmaceutical firms in Bangladesh.

3.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were;

- i. To determine the effect of education diversity on employee performance in the Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh
- ii. To establish how ethnic diversity influences employee performance in the Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh
- iii. To find out the effect of gender diversity on employee performance in the Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh
- iv. To find out how age diversity influences employee performance in the Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh

4. Literature Review

4.1 Employee Performance

Previous research on workplace diversity suggests that diversity can be either detrimental or beneficial for employee performance (Williams and O'Reilly, 1998). For instance, employee diversity is positively associated with creativity and problem-solving skills (Bantel and Jackson, 1989; Jehn et al., 1999) and negatively related with cohesiveness and cooperation (Pelled et al., 1999). Good work force diversity practices in the area of human resources are believed to enhance both employee and organizational performance (Adler, 1986). Furthermore, employee diversity allows increased creativity, a wider range of perspectives, better problem definition, more alternatives and better solutions (Adler, 1986). It is also argued that with decreasing homogeneity in the workforce, it has become crucial for organizations to develop equal opportunities and diversity management policies to maintain the skills of employees with diverse backgrounds in order to protect their competitive position in the market place (Gilbert and Ivancevich, 2000; Shaw, 1993).When corporate managers ignore the conflicts between co-workers, this will result in clashes amongst them. In turn, these

clashes will be converted into personal and emotional conflict in the long run and therefore damages the organizational culture, worker morale, and overall organizational performance. It can also lead to a reduction in creativity, innovation, quality, and performance of employees and organizations ultimately leading to negative effects on the team performance (Jehn, 1994).

4.2 Gender

Discrimination on hiring workers based on gender has resulted in a firm's hiring workers who are paid higher wages than alternative workers, but are no more productive (Barrington and Troke, 2001; Becker, 1971). We live in a male dominant world, with most cultures around the globe adhering to that notion. Consequently, many organizations prefer to hire men compared to women because men are perceived to have better performance and ability to manage their jobs and women are stereotyped against in those characteristics (Leonard and Levine, 2003; Nkomo, 1992; Heilman et al., 1989). According to Brown (2008) and Carr-Ruffino (2003), significant amount of workforce diversity remains ineffective if gender issues are not first recognized then in turn managed. The challenge is first to successfully overcome the thought that woman are not equal to man. Kossek et al., (2005) identified that only 54% of women are in the workforce worldwide compared to 80% of men. Nevertheless, according to Kochan et al., (2002), providing an equal job opportunity to women is vital to improve performance of employees in an organization. These societal mandates eliminated formal policies that discriminated against certain classes of workers and raised the costs to organizations that failed to implement fair employment practices.

Moreover, Wentling and Rivas (2000) study found that organizations with diverse workforce provide superior services and tap niche markets because they can understand customers better (Kundu, 2003). Kochan et al., (2002) argued that employees began to realize and recognize demographic differences such as gender differences affecting the working relationship between employees and their performance. Moreover, Jehn and Werner (1993) measured that diversity had a significant effect on group processes, but the nature of the effect depended on whether the diversity was in gender or not.

H1: There is a significant relationship between gender and employee performance

4.3 Age

Winnie (2008) found that youth, on one hand, are more willing to learn new things and accept new ideas and on the other hand, older people who have more life experiences are more mature and possess better problem-solving skills. It is argued that different age groups provide different values for companies and these values can complement each other which improve companies' performance. Age diversity has become an inevitable fact of life in many organizations (Kunze et al., 2011). There are two major theories which explain this relationship; the social identity and self-categorization respectively. Individuals are suggested to classify themselves into certain groups on the basis of dimensions that are personally relevant for them according to social identity and self-categorization theories (Kunze et al., 2011; Tajfel and Turner, 1986). As a result, individuals tend to favor members of their own group at the expenses of other groups, against which they may both stereotype and discriminate against (Kunze et al., 2011). Gellner and Stephen (2009) argued that age heterogeneity can negatively affect employee productivity due to differences in values and preferences of distinct age groups. It has also been shown that conflicts are particularly frequent in the presence of generation gaps (Gellner and Stephen, 2009; Lau and Murnighan, 2005; Pitcher and Smith 2001). Furthermore, age heterogeneity on its own has a negative effect on individual productivity (Gellner and Veen, 2009).

H2: There is a significant relationship between age diversity and employee performance

4.4 Education background

Daniel (2009) found that an employee will be more productive depending on the level of his/her education. The more education the individual received, the more productive the worker will be. Moretti (2004) argued that

cities with higher percentage of tertiary education level workers will enable individuals of all education level secure higher wages. Glaeser et al., (1995) found that a greater proportion of educated workers in a city translate to higher economic growth. Tracy and Sappington (1993) found that employers commonly reject hiring employees whose training, experience, or education is judged to be inadequate. This means that education background is critical to employees' employability level. Employees cannot find a job and perform well without adequate education background. Knight et al., (1999) found that education diversity was negatively related to decision-making consensus in top management teams. It seems that heterogeneous education backgrounds tend to increase the level of discomfort and conflict that may lead to decreased social integration in teams. In other words, education background diversity can have both advantages and disadvantages for employee performances toward organization.

H3: There is significant relationship between education background and employee performance

4.5 Ethnicity:

According to Zgourides et al.,(2002), the differences in cultural characteristics were predictive of team scores, which can be interpreted as the advantage of having ethnically different views for team problem solving. Members of the minority group can experience less job satisfaction, lack of commitment, problems with identity, perceived discrimination, etc. (Timmermans et al., 2011; Milliken and Martins, 1996; Harrison and Klein, 2007). According to Timmermans et al., (2011) study, ethnicity can be used as a proxy for cultural background and diversity in ethnicity can be expected to be positive for innovative performance. The growth of a multicultural workforce was the focus of the 90's and is gaining more momentum into the new era (Zgourides, Johnson and Watson (2002); Milliken and Martins, 1996; Nemetz and Christensen, 1996). Even though the nature of workforce composition is rapidly becoming more mixed in terms of gender, age, ethnicity, parallel interest has been increasing about the impact of such diversity in our educational institutions (Zgourides et al., 2002). Moreover, based on Timmermans et al. (2011) study some levels of diversity in ethnicity might be positive associated with innovation, high degree of diversity in ethnicity might be negative since it can create conflict and cliques due to social categorization (Dahlin, 2005).

H4: There is a significant relationship between ethnic diversity and employee performance

Limited empirical research demonstrated that diversity management can indeed improve organizational outcomes (Kalev, 2006; Ng and Burke, 2005; Pitts, 2009). The challenge and problems faced as a result of incorporating work place diversity under one roof can be turned into a strategic organizational asset if organizations are able to capitalize on this melting pot of diverse talents. With the mixture of talents of diverse cultural backgrounds, genders, ages, and lifestyles, an organization can respond to business opportunities more rapidly and creatively, especially in the global area which must be one of the important organizational goals to be attained. Furthermore, Hilary and Elaine (2000) suggested that organizations should embrace diversity in their workforce and work towards achieving it by creating a culture where difference can thrive, rather than working simply for representatives and assimilation. More importantly, if the organizational environment does not support diversity broadly, organizations risk losing talent to competitors.

Chan (2009) found that in order to effectively manage workplace diversity, the Human Resource Manager needs to maintain a cross cultural sensitivity competency by changing his/her management philosophy from an ethnocentric view (our way is the best way to do things) to a culturally relative perspective (let's take the best of a variety of ways). This shift in mindset has to be ingrained in the management style of Human Resource Managers in their basic management functions. It is argued that organizations that develop and employ the necessary policies and procedures to attract and retain the best and most qualified employees maintain a competitive advantage among their counterparts and subsequently increase their effectiveness.

To achieve success and maintain a competitive advantage, organizations draw on the most important resource, which is the skill set of the workforce. When work force diversity is not managed properly, there will be a

potential for higher voluntary employee turnover, difficulty in communication, and destructive interpersonal conflicts. Overall, it will be adversarial to organization's performance, profitability, and needless to mention, reputation. Decades of research on the effects of diversity within teams and small groups indicate that diversity can have negative effects, as well as positives ones (Kochan et al., 2003). Moreover they elaborated that the lack of evidence linking workforce diversity to employee performance may be that the relationship between diversity and the bottom line is more complex than is implied by the popular discussion.

5. Methodology

5.1 Sources of Data Collection:

Collecting data for conducting the study mainly have two sources. It includes primary sources and secondary sources. Sources are following:

5.1.1 Primary sources:

- ✓ Survey with questionnaire
- ✓ Conversations with employees

5.1.2 Secondary sources:

- ✓ Website of pharmaceutical companies
- ✓ Annual reports of pharmaceutical companies
- ✓ Reports collected from internal bodies.

5.2 Methods of Data Collection

5.2. Survey

There are two types of data collection method. To collect primary data regarding broad and specific objective, I did a questionnaire survey. The questionnaire includes close ended questions.

5.2.1. Close-ended questionnaire

The close-ended questionnaire was used to identify the present situation of employee performance and relationship between age, gender, educational background, ethnicity and employee performance through Likert scale for describing numerically and to show the level of governance in percentage, Likert's Five Scale model was being used in measuring and analyzing the data where 1 denotes strongly agree and 5 denotes strongly disagree. Close-ended questionnaire was also used to determine the appropriateness of existing policies.

5.3 Sampling Design:

5.3.1 Sampling element: In this report, sampling element was based on individuals only. They are the employees of who are accomplishing their regular duties to their jobs.

5.3.2 Sample Size: The sample size was 50 employees of respected fields.

5.3.3 Sampling Procedure: Non probability random sampling method was used to collect data from employees. When I found that some of the respondent didn't get interested to answer for questioning section then I went for snowballing sampling.

5.3.4 Sampling Distribution : The main focus of the research is on the some selected Pharmaceutical firms of our country .I covered the most popular pharmaceutical firms so that everyone can get a nearly clear idea about the impact of cross cultural issues on employee performance

Name of Pharmaceuticals firms	Target Number of employees
Square Pharmaceuticals Ltd	10
Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd	10
ACI pharmaceuticals Ltd	10
Incepta Pharmaceuticals Ltd	10
Beacon Pharmaceuticals Ltd	10
Total Sample Size	=50

Table 1: Distribution of Sample

5.4 Variables Covered

Figure 1: Showing dependent and independent variables

5.4.1 Gender: Gender differences have a great impact on the employee performances. Women in workplace face a wide practice called glass ceiling which means they are ignored when making promotion policy or promoting an employee especially in Asian countries. The research identified whether gender differences have any impact on employee performance and providing an equal job opportunity to women is vital to improve performance of employees in an organization or not .

5.4.2 Age: Generally, younger people are more capable of performing than the older. Age is also a big factor in promotion policy and in organizational hierarchy. Many Countries prefer older people for higher position in the organization. The study determined the impact of employee performance by analyzing the corporate environment where different ages of people are working

5.4.3 Ethnicity: Ethnicity influences the working environment of an organization. Its essential for HR manager to know that people from different groups have different work values. Studies have found that ethnic diversity has an influence in organizational culture and its effectiveness. Increased level of ethnicity can lead to complications in workplace and negative effect in the employees. In this variables the focus would be to identify the relationship between ethnic diversity and employee performance

5.4.4 Educational Background: The workplace of any organization will be much more effective and skilled if they possess strong educational background. It will help employees to understand the managerial decisions promptly. They will be technically sound. Educated employees are well aware of updating themselves in terms

of technology used in workplace. Good educational background provides better performance. In our study I identified that to what extent different educational backgrounds impact on performance

5.5 Analytical Tools

Descriptive statistics will be used to analyze data to get an overall situation. For the purpose of in-depth analysis, statistical tools, inter-correlation matrix and multiple regression techniques will be used. For data analysis, SPSS (Version: 20) will be used.

5.6. Data Analysis Method

5.6.1 Cronbach Alpha Method

Cronbach Alpha method was used to test the reliability and validity of data. Reliability refers to the consistency of set of items in measuring the study of variables. Cronbach alpha is most commonly used to analyze multiple Likert questions in a survey/questionnaire that form a scale.

5.6.2 Pearson Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis method was used to determine the numerical relationship between dependent variables and independent variables.

5.6.3 Regression Analysis

Four extracted dimensions were taken as independent variables against employee performance as dependent variable in a multiple regression to show the dependency of these variables.

5.6.4 T-test Method

For testing the hypothesis , t-test method was used and the hypothesis of this research would have been tested at 0.05 level of significance.

5.6 Limitations:

The limitations of the report including the following:

- Time is the key constraint of this report.
- Difficulty in collecting information because most of the information of selected pharmaceutical firms are confidential.
- Some of the directors are reluctant to provide feedback.
- Getting some relevant papers and documents are strictly prohibited.

6. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

6.1 Reliability of Data

Cronbach's alpha is commonly used method to measure the reliability or internal consistency that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group (Cooper & Schinder, 2001). It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. The satisfactory value in Cronbach's alpha is required to be more than 0.60 to be reliable (Malhotra, 2002).

Variables	Number of items	Value of Cronbach's Alpha
Gender	6	0.830
Age	4	0.782
Educational background	7	0.845
Ethnicity	5	0.756
Employee Performance	6	0.811

Test of Reliability of the Data

From the table, Gender diversity had a cronbach reliability alpha of 0.830, Age diversity had a cronbach reliability alpha of 0.782, Educational Background had a cronbach reliability alpha of 0.845, Ethnic diversity had a cronbach reliability alpha of 0.756 and Employee performance had a reliability alpha of 0.811. This clearly shows that the research instrument was reliable and hence no amendments were needed.

6.2 General Information

6.2.1 Gender of the respondent

Gender	Number	Frequency of Percent	Cumulative percent
Male	35	70%	70
Female	15	30%	100
Total	50	100%	100

70% of the total sample size was Male and 30% was female that means 35 respondents were male and 15 respondents were female out of 50

6.2.2 Age of the respondents

Years Old	Number	Frequency Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-29	15	30%	30
30-39	17	34%	64
40-49	12	24%	88
Over 50	6	12%	
Total	50	100%	100

Table shows age group of the respondents. Most of the respondents falls under the age group category of 30 - 39 years old (accounted for 34% or 17 respondents), followed by the age group of 20 -29 years old (30% or 15 respondents), 40 -49 years old (24% or 12 respondents), and 50 years old and above (12% or 6 respondents).

6.2.3 Education Level of the Respondents

Education Level	Number	Frequency Percent	Cumulative Percent
Honors	8	16%	16
Masters	35	70%	86
Diploma	4	8%	94
Phd	3	6%	
Total	50	100%	100

Most of the respondents were Master’s degree holders (70% or 35 respondents), followed by honors (16% or 8 respondents), diploma (8% or 4 respondents), and PhD (6% or 3 respondents).

6.2.4 Working Experience of the Respondents

Working Experience in Years	Number	Frequency Percent	Cumulative Percent
2-5 Years	15	30%	30
6-10	20	40%	70
11-15	7	14%	84
More than 15	8	16%	
Total	50	100%	100

The highest proportion of respondents with 6 – 10 years of working experience (40% or 20 respondents), followed by 2 - 5 years (30% or 15 respondents), 11 -15 years (14% or 7 respondents), and more than 15 years (16% or 8 respondents)

6.3 Correlation between the Dependent and the Independent Variables

		Employee Performance	Educational Background	Ethnic Diversity	Gender Diversity	Age Diversity
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.189**	.243**	.493**	.129
	Sig.(2 tailed)		.006	.000	.000	.062
	N	50	50	50	50	50
Educational Background	Pearson Correlation	.189**	1	.278**	.123	.091
	Sig.(2 tailed)	.006		.000	.071	.189
	N	50	50	50	50	50
Ethnic Diversity	Pearson Correlation	.243**	.278**	1	.330**	.196**
	Sig.(2 tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.004
	N	50	50	50	50	50
Gender Diversity	Pearson Correlation	.493**	.123	.330**	1	.251**
	Sig.(2 tailed)	.000	.071	.000		.000
	N	50	50	50	50	50
Age Diversity	Pearson Correlation	.129	.091	.196**	.251**	1
	Sig.(2 tailed)	.062	.189	.004	.000	
	N	50	50	50	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the findings, there is a positive association between education diversity and employees performance as shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.189 and a p-value of 0.006. The p-value is less than 0.05 and hence the association was significant. In addition, there is a positive and significant association between ethnic diversity and employee performance as shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.243 and a p-value of 0.000. Further, there is a positive significant association between gender diversity and employee performance. This is shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.493 and a p-value of 0.000. Lastly, the findings show that there is a positive association between age diversity and employee performance as shown by a p-value of 0.062.

6.4 Regression Analysis

A multivariate regression analysis was used to determine the weight of the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The multivariate regression model was:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4$$

Where:

Y = Employee Performance in the Pharmaceutical Industry

β_0 = Constant Term;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 = Beta coefficients;

X1= Gender diversity;

X2= Age diversity;

X3= Ethnicity diversity;

X4= Education diversity;

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.714	.635	.627	.28712

The R-Squared is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable (science) which can be explained by the independent variables. The R squared in this study was 0.635, which shows that the four independent variables (age diversity, education diversity, gender diversity, and ethnic diversity) can explain 62.7% of the dependent variable. This shows that the other factors not studied in this study explain 28.7% of the dependent variable (Employee performance in the pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh).

Model	Sum of the Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	15.675	4	3.932	18.564	.000
Residual	48.456	85	.212		
Total	64.131	89			

The analysis of variance in this study was used to determine whether the model is a good fit for the data. From the findings, the p-value was 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and hence the model is good in predicting how the four independent variables (age diversity, education diversity, gender diversity, and ethnic diversity) influence employee performance in the banking industry. Further, the F-calculated (18.545) was more than the F-critical (2.46) which shows that the models was fit in predicting the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Regression Coefficients

From the following table, unstandardized coefficients indicates how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable, when all other variables are held constant. The beta coefficient indicated that how and to what extent workforce diversity elements influence on employee performance of selected private firms in Bangladesh. It has been found that, Ethnic Diversity (beta =.549, t=6.269, p<0.05) have the highest impact on employee performance of the firms. On the other hand, Age diversity (beta=.332, t=2.590, p<0.05), Education diversity (beta =.286, t=4.299, p<0.05), and Gender Diversity (beta =.149, t=1.959, p<0.05), have a relatively lower impact on employee performance of the selected private firms of Bangladesh. The Regression Model is: Employee Performance = 0.573 + 0.149*X1(Gender) + 0.332*X2(Age) + 0.549*X3(Ethnicity) + 0.286*X4(Education).

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.573	.200		2.870	.005
Gender	.149	.076	.182	1.950	.005
Age	.332	.054	.335	2.590	.005
Ethnic	.549	.089	.598	6.269	.005
Education	.286	.070	.238	4.299	.005

6.5 Test of Hypothesis

The hypothesis of this research had been tested at 0.05 level of significance

Decision rule: Hypothesis will be accepted, if P value is less than significance level .and will be rejected if the P value is more than significance level

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	P Value	Significance level	T	Implications
Employee Performance	Gender	.001	.05	1.853	Accepted
	Age	.000	.05	2.334	Accepted
	Ethnicity	.000	.05	6.001	Accepted
	Education	.000	.05	3.998	Accepted

All the hypothesis mentioned in the literature review part were accepted because all of these filled up the condition of decision rule.

7. Proposed Areas for Further Studies

This study was limited to the pharmaceutical industry in Bangladesh and hence more studies should be conducted to focus on other sectors like the manufacturing industry or banking industry. The study also suggests that further studies should be conducted on the relationship between age diversity and employee performance in other sectors. In this study only four items of variables of workforce diversity were covered. Other items such as language diversity, social diversity, diversity in abilities can be used for further study. Further research can be conducted by expanding the sample size to better represent the population for better and more accurate results

8. Conclusion

The diverse workforce is providing a challenge to the organizations .It is very important to know the impact of workforce diversity on employee performance that leads to organizational performance. A diverse workforce is a reflection of changing business position and marketplace. In the laboratory research diverse work teams bring high value to organizations and respecting individual differences will benefit the workplace by creating competitive edge and increasing work productivity. Diversity management benefits associates by creating a fair and safe environment where everyone has access to the same opportunities and challenges.

Management tools in diverse workforce should be used to educate everyone about diversity and its issues, including laws and regulations. Most workplaces are made up of diverse cultures, so organizations need to learn how to adapt to be successful. The rate of workforce diversity is in increasing position of Bangladesh especially in pharmaceuticals firms. The main focus of the research was on the some selected Pharmaceutical firms of our country .The researcher covered the most popular pharmaceutical firms so that people get a nearly clear idea about the impact of cross cultural issues on employee performance Since the workforce diversity is becomes one of most popular ways to evaluate employee performance in an organization in recent year, the research tends to provide the evidence to support future research related to this field.

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